

PREVENTING COPYRIGHTS INFRINGEMENT OF IMAGES BY WATERMARKING IN TRANSFORM DOMAIN USING FULL COUNTER PROPAGATION NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

Images are undoubtedly the most efficacious and easiest means of communicating an idea. They are surely an indispensable part of human life .The trend of sharing images of various kinds for example typical technical figures, modern exceptional masterpiece from an artist, photos from the recent picnic to hill station etc, on the internet is spreading like a viral. There is a mandatory requirement for checking the privacy and security of our personal digital images before making them public via the internet. There is always a threat of our original images being illegally reproduced or distributed elsewhere. To prevent the misuse and protect the copyrights, an efficient solution has been given that can withstand many attacks. This paper aims at encoding of the host image prior to watermark embedding for enhancing the security. The fast and effective full counter propagation neural network helps in the successful watermark embedding without deteriorating the image perception. Earlier techniques embedded the watermark in the image itself but is has been observed that synapses of neural network provide a better platform for reducing the distortion and increasing the message capacity.

KEYWORDS

Watermarking , Full Counter Propagation Network, Transform Domain, Discrete Cosine Transform

1. INTRODUCTION

The world today is enjoying and availing numerous benefits of accessing internet almost from everywhere. There are advantages and disadvantages of everything so is true for the internet. The photographs/figures taken or drawn by us so deliberately after so many efforts must also be protected on the common media. There have been awkward and problematic cases of image forgery. To avoid the conflicts and headaches thereafter it is necessary to watermark the images beforehand to safeguard them. It is however impossible to stop anybody from copying watermarked images or distributing them but it is also true that watermarking poses challenges for those having malignant intentions. Removal of watermark may degrade the visual quality of image leaving it of no use. Thus digital watermarking is the process of authenticating the carrier images, audio, video etc with the insertion of some crucial information that may or may not have

relation to the carrier signal. It is a substantial and widely acceptable approach of securing the digital content worldwide.

There are two methods of watermarking namely visible and invisible. In the visible mode the logo or the text is positioned over the image as we see on the TV channels.

Figure 1 Visible watermarking

a) Original image b) Watermarked image

Figure 2 Invisible watermarking

Invisible watermarking hides the watermark so very well inside the image that it is almost impossible to detect its presence with naked eyes. The invisible method has got two variations namely robust and fragile watermarking. If the watermarked image sustains the attacks performed on it without any effect of watermark then it can be termed as robust watermarking. Given here in this paper is a methodology based on invisible robust watermarking. The secret encoding is done inside the transform domain taking into consideration factors like high embedding capacity and robustness over spatial domain. The full counter propagation neural network is opted for embedding the watermark by training the competitive network. The algorithm is substantially robust as it is successfully generating the watermark even after facing attacks one after another.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are basically two main methods for watermark embedding namely embedding in spatial domain and embedding in transform domain. We present here some of the popular techniques in each of the domain, followed by researchers worldwide for securing the images on the digital media.

2.1. Spatial Domain Embedding

Standard Images are represented /stored in spatial domain as well as in transform domain. The transform domain image is represented in terms of its frequencies; whereas, in spatial domain it is represented by pixels. In simple terms, transform domain means the image is segmented into multiple frequency bands. To transfer an image to its frequency representation, we can use several reversible transforms like Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT), Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), or Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT). Each of these transforms has its own

characteristics and represents the image in different ways. Watermarks can be embedded within images by modifying these values, i.e. the transform domain coefficients. In case of spatial domain, simple watermarks could be embedded in the images by modifying the pixel values or the Least Significant Bit (LSB) values. However, more robust watermarks could be embedded in the transform domain of images by modifying the transform domain coefficients.

The advantages of cryptography and imperceptibility of digital image watermarking in were combined in spatial domain [1]. The watermark being generated with the help of one-way hash function. Each bit of the watermark was then embedded into respective blocks of the original image, in raster scan order. The embedding was done keeping in mind the average contrast value of each block. The extraction procedure computed and compared the sum of the pixels values for the blocks of the original and watermarked image.

The difference expansion algorithm was implemented for achieving the lossless and high capacity data hiding inside prediction error [2]. Each index value was predicted by using the average of its four precedent neighbors. If the difference between the index value and its predictive value was found to be larger than a threshold, the pixel was skipped. Otherwise the four precedent neighbors were used to predict the current index during data embedding and retrieving. The prediction error of the indexed image reduced considerably. The algorithm allowed the data embedding process to be reversed and recovered the exact original indexed image without any distortion at all.

Watermarking of color images based on spatial domain by embedding watermark in saturation on the HSI space was carried out in the work done by kao et al.,[3].

Zhijua and jiping[4]came out with color image digital watermarking method based on valve-value surface. The valve value of curve surface of the original image is found to get the outline information of the original image; then embedding watermarks into the edge of the outline. This method has strong resistance to attacks like filtering and zooming.

Zeki A.M, Manaf A. A,[5] aimed at replacing the watermarked image pixels by new pixels that can protect the watermark data against attacks and at the same time keeping the new pixels very close to the original pixels in order to protect the quality of watermarked image. The technique is based on testing the value of the watermark pixel according to the range of each bit-plane.

Krishna V.V et al., [6] presented a novel fact , that by inserting the watermark using Least Significant Bit (LSB), the grey value of the image pixel either remains same or increases or decreases to one. Ambiguity of grey level values by LSB method comes between successive even and odd grey level values only. This approach allows high robustness, embedding capacity and enhanced security.

Ganeshan and Gupta [7] gave a scheme in which 12 binary images can be embedded in the spatial domain using LSB substitution technique in a single RGB image. The proposed scheme also provides an extra level of security to the watermark image by scrambling the image before embedding it into the host image.

Hussein Jamal A. [8]gave the idea of selecting 16 blocks of 8X8 from the center of colored RGB image converted to YCbCr color space , to embed the monochrome image. The selected blocks are chosen spirally among the blocks that have log-average luminance higher than or equal the log-average luminance of the entire image. Each byte of the monochrome watermark is added by updating a luminance value of a pixel of the image. If the byte of the watermark image represented white color (255) a value α is added to the image pixel luminance value, if it is black (0) the α is subtracted from the luminance value.

Dinu Coltuc[9] reduced the distortions due to watermarking by embedding the expanded difference into the current pixel and its prediction context.

Surekha and Swamy [10] explored the possibility of embedding multiple binary images simultaneously in the host image also they gave the way to iteratively embed the watermark in different locations of cover image for enhancing robustness.

Bamatraf et al.,[11] also emphasised the manipulation of least significant bit for watermarking because of the least possible effect on the quality of cover image. They inversed the binary values of the watermark text and shifting the watermark according to the odd or even number of pixel coordinates of image before embedding the watermark. There is a flexibility depending upon the length of the watermark text. If the length of the watermark text is more than $((M \times N)/8) - 2$, there is a way to embed the extra of the watermark text in the second LSB.

2.2. Transform Domain Embedding

The Barni M et al.,[12] expressed the idea of hiding the watermark within the color image by modifying a subset of full frame DCT coefficients of each color channel. The extraction was only possible by comparing the correlation with a threshold.

Ahmadi and Safabaksh [13] converted the original image into the NTSC color space for separating the grayscale information from color data followed by dividing the luminance component Y into 8X8 blocks and transforming it to DCT. To prevent tampering or unauthorized access, watermark permutation function was present.

Chin man-Pun [14] protected the image copyrights by DFT coefficients based watermarking. First, the original image was decomposed into DFT coefficients using a fast Fourier transform. For minimal loss in image fidelity, the watermark was embedded in those DFT coefficients with highest magnitudes except for those in the lowest one. Extraction did not require the cover image.

Yang and Jin [15] took the advantage of DCT and DWT coefficients for color image watermarking. Firstly, the green components of an original image are divided into blocks, for each of which DCT is calculated and from each of which DC components are chosen to make up a new image, and new images are transformed with Haar wavelets. Then, a binary image of scrambling chaotic encryption is embedded into a low frequency sub-band.

Gao Chang[16] embedded authentication information into color JPEG format images based on discrete wavelet transforms. Firstly acquiring the gray values matrix from the color image, then identifying low and high frequency coefficients by using a two-dimensional discrete wavelet transform. The authentication information was embedded into the low coefficients by modifying the low coefficients' mean values.

Manimaran et al., [17] devised a unique way of encrypting the watermark by DES method after compressing it and the cover image is DCT transformed, followed by embedding.

Poljicak, et al.,[18] used the magnitudes of the fourier transform for embedding. The PSNR values were chosen the means for evaluating the quality degradation. The method was robust enough to handle the print scan, print cam and the attacks from Stir Mark benchmark software.

Xie Bin [19] divided color image luminance component into 8x8 blocks for DCT transform in $b r Y C C$ Color Space, then embedded binary watermark in its middle frequency coefficients in DCT domain, therefore, the embedding and extraction of the binary watermark in color image carrier was implemented successfully. Blind extraction, to get back the watermark without original image, was also observed.

In an algorithm given in [20] based on the DCT domain, embedding a watermarking color image into a host color image was performed to protect the copyrights of color images. The coordinates of R,G and B components were scrambled by logistic mapping before those components were embedded. Then the scrambled R,G and B components in color spaces a used as watermarking sequences. The host image blocks classified by the luminance, contrast and textures. The characteristics of human visual system were explored and practiced, by which watermarking components with different strength could be embedded into different DCT coefficients of image blocks according to the above classification.

Frequency domain watermark embedding was also emphasized by Sengupta and Mandal[21] in 2011. Firstly the cover image was transformed into the time domain using 8x8 mask in row major order using DCT resulting in its corresponding frequency components. Highest frequency values were fetched from red and green components of transformed RGB matrix as watermark. A secret key and a hash function watermarks embedded into blue components of the cover image in spatial domain was the central idea.

2.3. Contribution of Neural Networks in Image Watermarking

The transform domain embedding when combines with the ultimate secure and fast to train artificial neural networks such as FCNN or RBF etc are surprisingly very efficient for the purpose of image watermarking.

Paper [22] proposed a color image watermarking algorithm based on fractal and neural networks in Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) domain. Firstly, the algorithm utilized the fractal image coding technique to obtain the characteristic data of a gray-level image watermark signal and encrypted it by a symmetric encryption algorithm before it was embedded. Secondly, by exploiting the abilities of neural networks and considering the characteristics of Human Visual System (HVS), a Just Noticeable Difference (JND) threshold controller was designed to ensure the strength of the embedded data adapting to the host image itself entirely. Thus the watermark scheme possessed dual security characteristics. CIELab color space was chosen to guarantee the stability of the results.

Kutter [23] proposed a watermarking scheme embedding the watermark bits into the blue channel of a color image. In Kutter's system, embedded watermark bits can be extracted with a threshold by considering the neighbor pixels relation. However, the watermarking system is vulnerable since the reference information, which decides the threshold, can be easily destroyed.

In order to improve the robustness of Kutter's system, Yu et al. [24] proposed an adaptive way to decide the threshold by applying neural network. Yu et al. hide an invisible watermark into the blue channel of a color image, and then cooperate with neural network to learn the characteristics of the embedded watermark related to the watermarked image.

A novel blind watermarking technique based on back propagation neural networks was proposed by Huang Song et al.,[25] in 2008. The scheme hid a scrambled watermark into an image, and took HVS characteristics into consideration during the watermark embedding process, then used a back propagation neural network to learn the characteristics of the embedded watermark related to the watermarked image. With the aid of the learning and adaptive capabilities of neural network, the trained neural network exactly recovered the watermark from the watermarked image.

Yi et al.,[26] proposed a novel digital watermarking scheme based on improved Back-propagation neural network for color images. The watermark was embedded into the discrete

wavelet domain of the original image and extracted by training the BPN which learnt the characteristics of the image. To improve the rate of learning and reduce the error, a momentum coefficient was added to the traditional BPN network.

Bansal and Bhadauria[27] solved the issues such as ‘Proprietary Net’ and ‘Sure Win’ by enhancing the security of images through DCT transform and encoding the secret bits in the high energy region ,thereafter presenting the encoded image to FCNN for embedding watermark.

Xu He, Chang Shujuan [28] proposed an adaptive image watermarking algorithm after studying the characteristics of Human Visual System and the association memory ability of neural network. The watermarking signal was embedded in higher frequency, which is in the lower frequency of original image by DWT joined with DCT.

Ramamurthy and Varadarajan (2012) [29] came up with a novel image watermarking approach based on quantization and back propagation neural network. The cover image was decomposed up to 3-levels using quantization and DWT. The bitmap was selected as a watermark. The back propagation neural network was implemented while embedding and extracting the watermark.

3. METHOD OF WATERMARK INSERTION

In the previous techniques there were problems related to robustness and imperceptibility. In the proposed approach we have reduced the distortion to a negligible level. As the cover image is not directly exposed for embedding the secret information instead we have suggested that synapses of neural network play a better platform for the watermark insertion. There was a chance of an unauthorized person claiming his ownership by extracting watermark for an unauthenticated image . The problem was “Proprietary FCNN”. A network can be trained in various ways to extract a watermark to prove ownership which is a threat to authentication.

With each different image, the competitive layer of the full counter propagation network chooses a winner that produce some or the other output watermark. It is quite possible that more than one input images resemble the weight pattern of the same neuron at the input layer. Thus, this neuron must be the winner in all the cases to produce the same watermark at the output layer for all the images. This raises problem of ‘Authenticity’, when one unauthentic image produces the correct watermark. The above problems require the need of an additional safety against counterfeiting. We have successfully encoded the cover image before actually directing it towards the real watermark embedding phase.

The following algorithm explains each step in detail:

The cover image (color image) size is given by $m_c \times n_c$, m_c being the no of rows and n_c being number of columns. The watermark image is of size $m_w \times n_w$.

The blocks are of 8×8 . ie blocksize = 8. The mid band matrix is chosen by user . In our algorithm it is a binary matrix of size 8×8 . It will help in encoding. The midband coefficients selection matrix is given as

$midband = [mid_{11}, mid_{12}, \dots, mid_{ij}, \dots, mid_{88}]$ for $1 \leq i \leq 8, 1 \leq j \leq 8$ and $mid_{ij} = 0$ or 1 .

$Sum_midband = \sum \sum midband(i,j)$

The message to be inserted is of the size

$Max_Message = (m_c \times n_c) / (blocksize)^2$

mm represents the number of rows in the encoding binary message matrix. nm represents the number of columns in the encoding binary message matrix. This message is generated by using random integer function of matlab.

$p=mc/8$ and $q=nc/8$

$R = p*q$ where R is total no of blocks of size $8x8$

$Pn_sequence = \text{round}(2*\text{rand}(1,\text{sum_midband})-0.5)$. This will generate the random numbers equal to number of mid band coefficients.

Repeat the following steps for $k=1$ to total no of blocks.

$x=1, y=1, k=1$, x is for progressing in the column wise direction. y is for progressing in the row wise direction. k is the variable which takes the blocks one by one.

Step 1- The cover image is divided into blocks of $8x8$ one by one.

Step 2- Each block is then transformed into its equivalent DCT coefficient block . Lets say the block is dct_block .

Step 3- If $message(k)=0$ then

```
{ for i=1 to 8
{ for j=1 to 8
{ if (midband(i,j) =1)
{ dct_block(i,j)= pn_sequence(pos);
pos=pos+1;
}end of if }end of for }end of for }// end of if
```

Step 4- Now convert the dct_block back to $idct$ ie inverse dct .

Step-5 Now x is incremented . If x exceeds the total number of columns , its reinitialized and next row is taken.

$x= x + \text{blocksize}$ if $(x+8)<nc$

$x=1$ and $y = y + \text{blocksize}$ for $(x+8)>nc$

Step 6 Increment $k =k+1$ (until $k=p*q$ ie total no of blocks in the host image)for encoding next block.

Step 7 Go to step 1 while $(k<=R)$

Step 8- The encoded image is converted to column vector in the following form-

Cover_Image= [$X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_{m \times n}$]

Where $m \times n$ is the total number of pixels in the cover image.

Also the watermark $W= [Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, \dots, Y_{m \times n}$]

Is converted to the column vector .

Step 9- The cover image and watermark are then supplied to the input layer of FCNN , followed by training the network to produce watermarked image and desired watermark at the output layer.

(Here to improve the imperceptibility we have chosen only the blue channel for encoding the message. Researchers round the globe agree that human eyes are less sensitive towards the blue color as compared to the red and green channels of a RGB image). Thus we observe that the problems related to unauthentic image giving correct watermark accidentally and the issue of generation of any watermark for every image is solved by encoding the cover image in DCT domain prior to neural network training.

We have chosen lenna and scenery color images as our cover images to train the network.

Figure 3 Original Cover Image Lenna.jpg Cover image2 Watermark image

The full counter propagation network has got the following architecture. It consists of three layers namely input layer, competitive layer and the output layer.

Figure 4 Architecture of Full Counter Propagation Neural Network

In the above figure W is the set of weights from Input layer cover image neurons to competitive layer. U is the set of weights from input layer watermark neurons to competitive layer. V is the set of weights from competitive layer neurons towards the output layer watermarked image neurons. T is the set of weights from competitive layer neurons to the output layer extracted watermark image neurons.

The training is carried out till the error is greater than predefined threshold otherwise the weights of every layer are adjusted. The entire training procedure of the full counter propagation network can be understood from the research paper of Chuan-Yu Chang, Sheng-Jyun Su, Hung-Jen Wang (2004)[30]. Lets understand the complete algorithm for watermark insertion through the following block diagram.

Figure 5 Process of embedding watermark

4. METHOD FOR WATERMARK EXTRACTION

The Full counter propagation network is particularly useful in watermarking as it yields a more robust watermarking solution. Also FCNN possesses higher embedding capacity without much degradation of the original information. It can remember the watermark image in itself and is helpful in extracting the same image for every authentic input cover image. An unauthorized person will not be able to claim his rights over the image as he would not be able to decode the original cover image which is the first step towards proving the authority. Once the decoding is done successfully there after the IDCT image is supplied to the FCNN for watermark extraction. Algorithm for extracting the watermark image form the FCNN is explained step wise below:- Midband matrix and blocksize is the same as the embedding algorithm.

R = total no of blocks of size 8×8 in the cover image which will be required in the dct domain embedding. Watermarked image is of size $m_w \times n_w$. The binary message is of size $m_m \times n_m$. The $pn_sequence_zero$ is the same as in the embedding algorithm.

Initialize the variables $x=1, y=1$

Let $enco_image(i1:i2)$ be defined to select the block containing all elements $(i1:i2)$ such that $x \leq i1 \leq x+blocksize-1$,
 $y \leq i2 \leq y+blocksize-1$,

Repeat the following steps R times to check the R blocks of the watermarked image for getting the decoding bits .

Step 1- The DCT coefficient block of watermarked image is obtained blockwise as under

Dct_block = DCT(enco_image(11:12))

The initial index of dct_block is set ind=1

Embedded sequence is obtained as given below:

Sequence(pos)= Dct_block(i,j),

for $1 < i < \text{blocksize}$, $1 < j < \text{blocksize}$, $\text{midband}(i,j)=1$

where, for all new pair (i,j) , $\text{pos}=\text{pos}+1$

Step 2- Correlation of the above obtained sequence is done with zero sequence

Correlate(k)= corr(pn_sequence_zero, sequence)

//Predefined function for correlation exists in matlab

Now x is incremented if x exceeds the total number of columns, it is reinitialized and next row is taken.

$x=x+\text{blocksize}$ for $(x+8)<nw$

$x=1$ and $y=y+\text{blocksize}$ for $(x+8)>nw$

Step 3- $K = k+1$ Go to step 1 while $(k \leq R)$

Step 4- Now after all the sequence is with us. Lets find out the message from the correlation of the two sequences as given below-

Message_ex (ee)= 0 for $\text{correlate}(ee)>0.5$

Message_ex(ee)=1 otherwise for every ee: $1 \leq ee \leq mm \times nm$

Step 5- A Boolean variable flag is checked ie if $\text{flag} = 1$, for every i such that $\text{message_ex}(i)=\text{message}(i)$ then we can say that our decoding is successful.

for $1 \leq i \leq mm \times nm$ (range of i)

Step 6- if $\text{flag}=0$

Then image is not authentic and it is not supplied to counter propagation network for extracting the watermark.

Figure 6 Process of watermark extraction

5. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

We have calculated the Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Normalized Correlation(NC) which are measures of imperceptibility and robustness. To find out Peak Signal to Noise Ratio we need to calculate some figures first. Mean Square Error between the gray level versions of the original cover image and the watermarked image.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{m \ n} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} [I(i, j) - K(i, j)]^2$$

Mean Square Error MSE calculates the mean square difference between the pixel values of Cover image I and Watermarked Image K.

The PSNR is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 PSNR &= 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{MAX_I^2}{MSE} \right) \\
 &= 20 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{MAX_I}{\sqrt{MSE}} \right) \\
 &= 20 \cdot \log_{10} (MAX_I) - 10 \cdot \log_{10} (MSE)
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, MAX_I is the maximum possible pixel value of the image. When the pixels are represented using 8 bits per sample, this is 255. For color images with three RGB values per pixel, the definition of PSNR is the same except the MSE is the sum over all squared value differences divided by image size and by three. Alternately, for color images the image is converted to a different color space and PSNR is reported against each channel of that color space, e.g., YCbCr or HSL.

Normalized Correlation NC is given by-

$$NC = \frac{\sum \sum [K(i,j)K'(i,j)]}{\sum \sum [K(i,j)K(i,j)K'(i,j)K'(i,j)]}$$

Attacks were also performed on the watermarked image to check the level of robustness ie the watermark can be extracted successfully even after trying to remove by illegal parties. Given below is a comparative study of PSNR with some of the popular attacks.

Table 1 PSNR values after performing attacks

Name of the attack	PSNR in Db	NC
No Attack	106.38 Db	0.9476
Salt & Pepper(SP) Noise, d=0.0001	97.9 Db	0.0025
(SP)Noise density d=0.001	82.83 Db	0.0025
d = 0.02	52.18 Db	0.0025
d = 0.05	43.33 Db	0.0025
Speckle Noise	62.56 Db	0.0025
Compression (resizing the image to 200x200 from 256x256)	84.62 Db	0.9476
Compression(resizing the image to 180x180 from 256x256)	92 Db	0.9476

The experiments were conducted on a system which has following system properties:-

Intel Core i5-2430 M CPU @ 2.40 GHz, 4.00 Gb RAM, 64 bit operating system. Windows 7 Home Basic, Copyright 2009 Service Pack 1. Matlab version 7.9 was used.

The constants chosen for training the Full Counter Propagation Neural Network for embedding the watermark and extraction.

Number of neurons in the hidden layer= 10
 The learning rate for input layer $\alpha=0.4$
 The Learning rate for the output layer $\beta=0.3$
 $k=0$
 $e=\text{infinity}$

The mid band matrix of 8x8 for selecting the blocks to be encoded is

```
[0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1
1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1
1 1 1 1 1 1 1 1]
```

This matrix is useful in selecting the DCT block for encoding the secret message. We have chosen a value =1 ie if $\text{midband}(i,j)=1$ then only encode that respective DCT block. The idea of encoding can further be proceeded for all the three channels that is red, green, blue. We can also embed a colorful watermark in all of them. These are certain modifications in the strategy suggested here which I am working on currently.

6. CONCLUSION

The idea of safeguarding images with watermarking in transform domain of image using full counter propagation neural network has proven its efficiency in terms of robustness, imperceptibility of watermark, capacity of information hiding and several other important parameters. It can go a long way in preserving the copyrights information of colorful digital images by experimenting with the other transform domains such as DWT, DFT. Image watermarking however is not limited to authenticating of digital information online but it has also proven its worth in fields like medicinal science, criminal investigation remote education , secured electronic voting system, health and insurance companies. In short we can implement watermarking to secure any sensitive image of importance in any sense.

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